

OCTANE NUMBER DESCRIPTION OF ETHERS

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Octane number is an indicator that characterizes the detonation resistance (explosion resistance) of fuel used in internal combustion engines with external mixture formation (usually gasoline, not used to characterize diesel fuel and aviation kerosene). The octane number is determined on a standard single-cylinder engine with a variable compression ratio. Gasoline with a higher octane number can withstand a higher compression ratio in the engine cylinders without premature self-ignition (engine knocking, "detonation") and therefore can be used in engines with higher specific power and efficiency [1].

Due to the rise in oil prices and the restriction of the use of thermal power plants in recent years, in many countries of the world there has been a tendency towards the increasing use of oxygen-containing compounds in commercial high-octane motor gasoline. Among oxygen compounds, methyl (MA), ethyl (EA) and methyl-tert butyl ether (MTBE), which have high octane numbers and low boiling points, are widely used, which allows increase the head fractions and thereby improve the distribution coefficient of the diesel engine, as well as a sufficiently high calorific value [2].

Why does ether ignite so easily? It is extremely difficult to answer this question, since we know very little about the chemistry of combustion, the chemistry of explosions, etc. There is a so-called flash point - the minimum temperature that a given substance must reach in order to ignite if it is set on fire. So, the flash point of ether is lower than that of gasoline and most solvents that are used in the laboratory: diethyl ether -49°C , gasoline (octane number 100) -38°C , benzene 11°C and ethyl alcohol 13°C .

Isopropyl ether (Isopropyl ether), which is a by-product, can be used to increase the octane number of gasoline (added to gasoline in an amount of 20%). The yield of isopropyl alcohol reaches 95-99%, and flourine-butyl alcohol - 90%. Most isopropyl alcohol is used to produce acetone, a significant amount is used as a solvent, in the form of esters, as antifreeze, etc.

Oxygenation has been part of the strategy to produce gasoline with the required octane rating since the late 1970s, and attempts have been made to use a range of alcohols and ethers for this purpose. All oxygenated fuels reduce the release of carbon monoxide (CO) and unburned.

MTBE and ETBE. The octane numbers of ethers are slightly lower than those of methyl and ethyl alcohols, but this is compensated by other advantages, which include low toxicity, good compatibility with fuel and hydrolytic stability, and high anti-corrosion properties

Oxygen-containing substances with an octane mixing number of 120-150 points (lower aliphatic alcohols, methyl tert-butyl ether) are also used as high-octane additives for gasoline.

Isopropyl alcohol is used in the chemical industry as a substitute for ethyl alcohol in various processes where its participation is required, such as the production of alcoholates, ethers, etc. At one time, isopropyl alcohol was used in large quantities for the production of diisopropyl ether, proposed as an anti-knock component (octane number 100) to motor fuel. In the perfume industry, isopropyl alcohol has found use instead of ethyl alcohol in the manufacture of perfumes and especially colognes. But the bulk of isopropyl alcohol is used to produce acetone.

Currently, there is a worldwide trend towards eliminating the introduction of organic lead compounds into gasoline. The introduction of organic lead compounds increased the octane number of gasoline. To improve the quality of gasoline and increase its octane number, you can use lower alcohols - C1 - CH and methyl tert-butyl ether (MTBE). Therefore, there is a need for a simple and rapid method for the determination of these oxygen-containing compounds in gasoline. The work describes a multidimensional GC method used for the analysis of gasoline-alcohol mixtures. It uses a large diameter quartz COT column.

References:

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